

Assessing the Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Green Logistics Management of Enterprises in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Green logistics supply management aims to achieve the goal of greening the economy, which is a global issue and goal for all countries. This is also the basis for implementing green logistics development in Vietnam.

Objective: The study aims to identify the critical factors influencing green logistics management and proposes policy recommendations for enhancing the application of green logistics in the supply chain and helping businesses increase competitiveness and sustainable development.

Methodology: The authors employed quantitative survey in prominent cities, including Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai Province, Binh Duong Province, and Ba Ria-Vung Tau Province. The survey participants for data collection were managers of enterprises related to green logistics activities. The data collection strategy involves direct interviews via a structured questionnaire with a sample size of 800 managers. The data were analysed using SPSS version 20.0 and Amos software.

Result: The study identifies eight critical factors influencing green logistics management at a significance level of 0.01 and eight accepted hypotheses. Technological advancements and innovations had the most substantial impact on green logistics management in Vietnam.

Conclusion: The study offers policymakers and industry executives significant insights, emphasising the importance of prioritising technology, resource sustainability, and waste management while creating a supporting legislative and organisational framework to achieve comprehensive green logistics management.

Unique Contribution: The study highlights the significant influence of technological advancements and innovations on green logistics management at enterprises in Vietnam.

Key Recommendation: Technological advancements and innovations should be prioritized by providing fiscal incentives, such as tax credits, subsidies, or grants, to encourage investment in green technologies like electric vehicles, automated warehousing, and renewable energy systems.

Keywords: Social responsibility; management; organizational culture; technology and innovations.

Introduction

Green logistics aims to create sustainable business value while balancing economic efficiency and environmental protection. Simply put, green logistics in the supply chain will incorporate environmentally friendly factors into the management process and use modern equipment to minimise air pollution, noise, waste, etc. Green logistics requires close coordination between the government, businesses, and the community, aiming to diversify green solutions in the supply chain in all aspects, such as green transportation, logistics data management (Khan et al., 2024).

The benefits of applying green logistics in the supply chain through the implementation of green logistics are considered an essential link in the “greening” of the supply chain, improving competitiveness and the sustainable development roadmap of the enterprise. This model brings many positive benefits such as: (1) Environmentally friendly based on the green supply chain management can help companies reduce Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions effectively by some simple methods such as reducing the use of non-renewable energy (oil, coal, and gas), limiting deforestation, conserving natural resources, reducing - reusing – recycling (Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021; Ahmad et al., 2022).

Green logistics also enhances compliance with environmental laws and regulates natural resources used to produce goods and provide services at the lowest level. Thanks to the above activities, the environment has significantly reduced pollution while effectively maintaining clean and fresh air. (2) Protecting human health by applying green logistics also protects human health. Specifically, the “greening” of logistics will take technology as the foundation and use green means of transport, mainly using clean materials that do not harm the environment. Thereby contributing to the elimination of greenhouse gas emissions and pollutants. (3) Optimise costs and improve supply chain quality (Amjad et al., 2022; Zhang & Mohammad, 2024).

In addition to the outstanding benefits for the environment and society, the application of green logistics in the supply chain not only helps optimise costs but also contributes to increasing transportation efficiency. Accordingly, businesses can implement green transportation by combining orders for the same trip, choosing reasonable traffic routes so that the truck is full of goods in both directions, etc. This will help reduce the number of empty trucks or trucks carrying goods halfway on the road to save fuel and transportation costs, while reducing traffic congestion and pollution caused by traffic. (4) Minimising industrial waste through the green logistics implemented in the supply chain also helps businesses effectively use natural ecological resources that are environmentally friendly. Specifically, businesses can use packaging made from recycled, biodegradable materials or pack goods in pallets (Wang & Ozturk, 2023). Reducing packaging waste, recycling old products, and recovering necessary values will create competitive advantages, increase flexibility, and strengthen links with partners. Therefore, the study aims to determine critical factors influencing green logistics management and propose policy recommendations for enhancing green logistics management at enterprises in Vietnam.

Literature review and hypothesis development

Green logistics management (GLM)

Green logistics management manages logistics activities to minimise adverse environmental impacts throughout the supply chain. This concept includes efficient transportation and storage of

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goods and seeks to optimise processes to reduce energy consumption, lower carbon emissions, and manage waste effectively (Ahmad et al., 2022). Green logistics emphasizes using sustainable technologies and processes, such as transporting goods with low-emission vehicles or recycling packaging. These activities range from selecting recyclable materials, optimising transportation routes, using renewable energy for warehouses and vehicles, and developing reverse logistics processes for product recovery, recycling, or reuse (Banihashemi et al., 2022). One of the main objectives of green logistics management is to create sustainable value for the company, society, and the environment. By minimising adverse effects on the ecosystem and complying with environmental regulations, green logistics contributes to building a positive image for businesses and plays a crucial role in long-term sustainable development strategies.

Environmental regulations and policies (ERP)

Regulations mainly drive green logistics. Domestic and international legislation, such as the Paris Agreement, the EU Emissions Trading System, and individual country laws about greenhouse gas emissions, influence corporations' actions. Businesses are now compelled by law to lessen their harmful effects on the environment by cutting down on emissions, trash, and resource use, thanks to these rules (Wang & Ozturk, 2023). Businesses adopt more sustainable activities due to carbon prices, while green certification incentives promote compliance with ecologically friendly standards. The authors gave hypothesis H1 in Figure 1.

Technological advancements and innovations (TAI)

Technology integration is crucial in green logistics, especially with IoT, AI, and big data analytics, which improve real-time logistics monitoring, optimization, and control. Electric and hydrogen vehicles minimize fossil fuel use, while route optimization algorithms cut emissions (Ali et al., 2023). Automatic warehousing systems save energy and improve storage and retrieval efficiency. Thus, technology goes beyond cost savings to make logistics more sustainable (Zhang & Mohammad, 2024), and the authors gave hypothesis H2 in Figure 1.

Supply chain collaboration and integration (SCI)

Green logistics demands supply chain-wide cooperation. Co-loading and shared distribution networks reduce empty loads and maximize vehicle use. A holistic green supply chain, resource reduction, and industrial sustainability require partnerships with eco-friendly suppliers and third-party logistics providers (Wang et al., 2022). Green logistics requires supply chain coordination to coordinate eco-friendly operations with suppliers, distributors, and other partners. The authors gave hypothesis H3 in Figure 1.

Energy efficiency in operations (EEO)

Green logistics relies on energy efficiency to cut fuel use and waste. Effective energy efficiency strategies include load consolidation, mode transitions to rail or sea, lower-emission road transport, and renewable warehouse energy sources (Junaid et al., 2022). Studies show that hybrid transport models reduce reliance on high-emission transport modes, helping meet environmental targets. Green logistics relies on energy efficiency to reduce emissions and costs (Taghavi, 2022), and the authors proposed hypothesis H4 in Figure 1.

Waste minimization and sustainable packaging (WSP)

Green logistics requires waste management to reduce packaging, product, and operation waste. Biodegradable and recyclable packaging reduces environmental effects and attracts eco-conscious consumers (Phonthanukitithaworn et al., 2024). Circular economy logistics practices such as waste-to-energy, material recycling, and packaging for end-of-life recyclability support sustainable development and reduce landfill use (Jinru et al., 2021). Green logistics requires waste reduction and sustainable packaging, especially for businesses with high packaging waste. The authors gave hypothesis H5 in Figure 1.

Resource availability and sustainable sourcing (RSS)

Sustainable resources like biofuels, recyclables, and renewable energy affect green logistics. Certified sustainable suppliers and renewable energy for shipping and warehousing lessen logistics' environmental impact (Song et al., 2022). These materials are scarce and expensive, which can hinder green logistics plans. To avoid disruptions, logistical operations must regularly analyze sustainable resource availability and reliability. Sustainable resources like renewable energy and recyclable materials also affect green logistics, and the authors gave hypothesis H6 in Figure 1.

Organizational culture (OC)

Company culture matters because CSR-focused organizations are more likely to institutionalize green logistics. Positive stakeholder views and stronger reputations can boost these organizations' consumer loyalty and market standing (Füchtenhans et al., 2023; Osman, 2022). Value chain shifts, market trends toward sustainable production and consumption, global minimum tax issues, new green development, environmental protection, and climate change requirements challenge small and medium-sized businesses. Promoting an eco-friendly workplace and sustainable development. The companies' organisational culture also affects green logistics adoption and maintenance (Iddik, 2024), and the authors gave hypothesis H7 in Figure 1.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR)

CSR commitments heavily influence logistics tactics, which encourage green practices as part of an ethical goal. Corporate strategy includes CSR initiatives, with logistics a priority. Businesses promote the economy and have a big responsibility to society as technology and the Internet advance (Hong et al., 2023). Corporate social responsibility includes defending consumer rights, employee working conditions, the environment, and community contributions to comply with laws and regulations (Firoozi & Keddie, 2022). CSR's quick growth and vast influence have made it increasingly important and complicated for logistics companies. Profit-making firms must actively promote social sustainability, and the authors gave hypothesis H8 in Figure 1.

Based on the above, green logistics expansion enhances a nation's production and output. It is crucial in sustainable development, facilitating access to significant initiatives and research, and producing high-quality green logistics services. It also enhances productivity and facilitates numerous options for international collaboration. The authors utilise the theory of green logistics and incorporate local and foreign studies to develop a research model on how these eight factors

determine the effectiveness and adoption rate of green logistics management among Vietnamese enterprises. The authors proposed the model in Figure 1.

Source: Authors own work

Figure 1: A research model for critical factors affecting green logistics management

Figure 1 shows eight independent factors influencing green logistics management of enterprises in Vietnam: (1) Environmental regulations and policies (ERP), (2) Technological advancements and innovations (TAI), (3) Supply chain collaboration and integration (SCI), (4) Energy efficiency in operations (EEO), (5) Waste minimization and sustainable packaging (WSP), (6) Resource availability and sustainable sourcing (RSS), (7) Organizational culture (OC), (8) Corporate social responsibility (CSR). Figure 1 also shows that green logistics management (GLM) is the dependent factor.

Research methods

This research consists of three steps: (1) conducting qualitative research, (2) quantitative (preliminary) research, and (3) formal quantitative research through the following procedures outlined in the article as part of the ranking's research and development process:

First, the authors must settle on an environmentally friendly logistics management theory to serve as the basis for the conceptual framework and study problem. The first part of the investigation involved doing three analyses: (1) Establish a theoretical foundation for the study of green logistics management concepts; (2) Examine the relationships between the concepts in the research model; (3) Create a preliminary scale for the concepts in the study, which is the scale of factors impacting green logistics management.

Secondly, the authors conduct empirical research and focus groups with nine corporate managers from different provinces and cities in Vietnam, such as Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai, Binh Duong, and Ba Ria-Vung Tau, to develop conceptual measurements for green logistics management. At the same time, to get suggestions about the scope of green logistics management, the writers interviewed and surveyed fifteen logistics professionals (Hair et al., 2018).

Thirdly, the authors interviewed fifteen logistics experts in Vietnam for the preliminary quantitative study. Since the questionnaire established after step 2 evaluates green logistics management, it is appropriate for this study's survey of logistics managers. Fifteen logistics professionals make up the sample size. Many Vietnamese cities and provinces, including important urban areas like Ho Chi Minh City, Binh Duong Province, Dong Nai Province, and Ba Ria-Vung Tau Province, were questioned by logistics experts.

Fourthly, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha will be applied to the data collected in Step 3 to conduct a preliminary scale assessment. Using a random, non-probability sampling technique, initial quantitative research was conducted from 15/01/2024 to 15/06/2024 in Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai Province, Binh Duong Province, and Ba Ria - Vung Tau Province to evaluate the modified scale. The sample size was 800 logistics managers based on Table A1 - Research questionnaires, with only 745 votes processed. The authors used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to determine if the conceptual scale is legitimate. The authors conducted CFA and SEM studies after identifying EFA. The load factor should equal or greater than 0.3 to guarantee factor difference. Half of the total variation was excised. When the value of KMO is greater than or equal to 0.5, the Bartlett test is statistically significant < 0.05 .

Finally, the data was tested for scale reliability using Cronbach's alpha. After analyzing the system's amount, the writers reevaluated rank reliability. Data from formal research determines Cronbach's alpha. The authors assessed scale value using the SEM framework's EFA and CFA. Cronbach's alpha is done in step 6, and in step 5, data is created on an EFA-based scale. The CFA method evaluates measure dependability. Substituting EFA and CFA into SEM (Hair et al., 2018). This step-in model evaluation and hypothesis testing developed the standard scale and analyzed the SEM structure. Structural equation modeling evaluates theoretical frameworks and research lines' adaptability.

The model tests led the authors to offer governance implications. The authors constructed a research model, conducted the investigation, and combined theoretical underpinnings with domestic and foreign studies. The authors initially created a study model to test the expected scale's reliability and validity. After designing and testing the scale, they obtained early data from fifteen logistics professionals. After this, the authors obtained official data to test their hypothesis and model. The authors suggested policy changes to improve green logistics management.

Research results and discussions

Analysis of descriptive statistics and Cronbach's alpha for factors affecting green logistics management

Table 1: *Testing descriptive statistics and Cronbach's alpha for green logistics management*

Items	Cronbach's alpha	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Environmental regulations and policies (ERP: ERP1, ERP2, ERP3, ERP4)	0.875	2.392	0.676
2. Technological advancements and innovations (TAI: TAI1, TAI2, TAI3, TAI4)	0.958	3.087	0.991
3. Supply chain collaboration and integration (SCI: SCI1, SCI2, SCI3, SCI4, SCI5)	0.909	2.405	0.685
4. Energy efficiency in operations (EEO: EEO1, EEO2, EEO3)	0.944	3.342	0.972
5. Waste minimization and sustainable packaging (WSP: WSP1, WSP2, WSP3, WSP4)	0.965	3.072	0.982
6. Resource availability and sustainable sourcing (RSS: RSS1, RSS2, RSS3, RSS4)	0.856	3.392	0.923
7. Organizational culture (OC: OC1, OC2, OC3, OC4)	0.952	3.059	0.976
8. Corporate social responsibility (CSR: CSR1, CSR2, CSR3, CSR4)	0.950	3.052	0.984
9. Green logistics management (GLM: GLM1, GLM2, GLM3)	0.946	3.349	0.970

Source: Authors own work

Table 1 tests for analysis of descriptive statistics and Cronbach’s alpha for green logistics management factors following: (1) Environmental regulations and policies (ERP) with an alpha of 0.875, a mean of 2.392, and a standard deviation of 0.676. With a reliability score of 0.875, the items measure a cohesive construct, suggesting internal solid consistency. (2) Technological advancements and innovations (TAI) with a 0.958 Cronbach's Alpha, a 3.087 Mean, and a 0.991 Standard Deviation. Items measuring technical advances and innovations have a high Cronbach's alpha of 0.958, indicating outstanding dependability. (3) Supply chain collaboration and integration (SCI) with a 0.909 Cronbach's Alpha, a 2.405 Mean, and a 0.685 Standard Deviation for the Supply Chain Collaboration and Integration (SCI) scale. The five items that comprise the construct have a Cronbach's alpha of 0.909, meaning they are very reliable.

Table 2: Testing critical factors affecting green logistics management (EG)

Relationships	Standardized estimate	S.E	C.R	P value	Result
GLM ← ERP	0.084	0.054	3.584	0.001	Accepted H1
GLM ← SCI	0.079	0.049	2.578	0.010	Accepted H3
GLM ← EEO	0.083	0.033	2.915	0.004	Accepted H4
GLM ← RSS	0.174	0.033	5.213	0.001	Accepted H6
GLM ← OC	0.080	0.024	2.837	0.005	Accepted H7
GLM ← TAI	0.532	0.030	16.540	0.001	Accepted H2
GLM ← CSR	0.087	0.031	2.693	0.007	Accepted H8
GLM ← WSP	0.123	0.024	4.337	0.001	Accepted H5

Source: Authors own work

Table 2 provides an analysis of the critical factors influencing green logistics management (GLM) based on standardized estimates, standard errors (S.E.), critical ratios (C.R.), and p-values for each hypothesized relationship. Below is a more academically rigorous interpretation of each relationship and its implications for green logistics management. The results indicated that all eight hypothesized factors have statistically significant positive effects on green logistics management,

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as evidenced by their p-values (< 0.05). However, the magnitude of these effects varies considerably. Technological advancements and innovations (0.532) exhibit the most substantial influence, underscoring the critical role of technology in facilitating sustainable logistics practices.

Resource availability and sustainable sourcing (0.174), waste minimization, and sustainable packaging (0.123) show notable positive effects, reflecting the importance of both sustainable sourcing and waste management in green logistics. Lower-Impact Factors: Other factors, such as environmental regulations (0.084), energy efficiency (0.083), organisational culture (0.080), supply chain collaboration (0.079), and CSR (0.087), demonstrate positive but comparatively lower impacts. While essential, these elements may require reinforcement through policy support, technological integration, or enhanced organisational commitment to produce more substantial effects. The findings suggest that Vietnamese enterprises aiming to strengthen green logistics management should prioritise technological innovation, sustainable sourcing, and waste minimisation as primary strategies. These areas represent high-impact factors and can deliver substantial gains in sustainability. Moreover, reinforcing organisational culture, enhancing supply chain collaboration, and embedding CSR principles could further support the implementation of green logistics, though these factors alone may have a limited impact without solid technological and regulatory frameworks.

Source: Authors own work

Figure 2: Testing for various factors affecting green logistics management (GLM)

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Figure 2 showed that the assessment of the critical factors affecting green logistics management: CMIN/DF = 3.422 (<5.0), GFI = 0.885 (>0.800), TLI = 0.945 (>0.900), CFI = 0.954 (> 0.900) and RMSEA = 0.057 (<0.08). The article aims to determine the five factors affecting green logistics management in Vietnam, especially the technological advancements and innovations' most substantial impact on green logistics management in Vietnam, with a standardized estimate of 0.532, which is the most important. In conclusion, this study offers a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing green logistics management, highlighting the multidimensional nature of sustainable practices within logistics. The insights serve as a foundation for developing targeted strategies and policies that address each factor's varying degrees of influence on green logistics outcomes.

Table 3: Testing Bootstrap 40.000 samples for factors affecting green logistics management

Parameter			SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias	C.R	Results
GLM	←	ERP	0.057	0.000	0.177	0.008	0.005	1.60	Accepted H1
GLM	←	SCI	0.049	0.000	0.123	0.004	0.003	1.33	Accepted H3
GLM	←	EEO	0.040	0.000	0.087	0.001	0.002	0.50	Accepted H4
GLM	←	RSS	0.043	0.000	0.166	0.005	0.003	1.67	Accepted H6
GLM	←	OC	0.024	0.000	0.060	0.007	0.004	1.75	Accepted H7
GLM	←	TAI	0.043	0.000	0.497	0.000	0.002	0.00	Accepted H2
GLM	←	CSR	0.035	0.000	0.085	0.002	0.003	0.67	Accepted H8
GLM	←	WSP	0.026	0.000	0.094	0.001	0.003	0.33	Accepted H5

Source: Authors own work

Table 3 showed that the factors impacting green logistics management were examined using Bootstrap testing with 40.000 samples at a significant threshold of 0.01 (C.R < 1.96), as shown in Table 3. This result perfectly aligns with Vietnamese applied logistics theory and practice tenets. Policymakers can use this result as scientific evidence to inform their forecasts.

Discussion of findings

Green logistics management integrates activities, organizations, information, people, and other resources to convey goods and services from producers, suppliers, and consumers. Green logistics management is also crucial to economic growth. Supply chain growth has offered various commercial and job possibilities, increasing Vietnamese enterprises' worldwide competitiveness. Moreover, the results in Table 2 display the results and highlight key aspects affecting organizations' green logistics management and detailed results for each factor:

(1) Tech-related discoveries and innovations showed that technological developments affect green logistics (GLM) with a standardized estimate of 0.532 and a p-value less than 0.001 in Table 2. As shown in Table 2, RSS enhances green logistics by a normalized estimate of 0.174 and a p-value less than 0.001 (Ali et al., 2023). This shows that sustainable resources and eco-friendly materials boost GLM. WSP also moderately affects GLM, as demonstrated by waste minimisation and sustainable packaging (WSP), with a standardised estimate of 0.123 and a p-value less than 0.001 (Phonthanukitithaworn et al., 2024). As part of the circular economy, green logistics benefits from waste reduction and sustainable packaging.

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(2) According to environmental laws and policies (ERP), ERP has a small but significant impact on GLM based on the standardised estimate = 0.084, $p < 0.001$ in Table 2 (Wang and Ozturk, 2023; Banihashemi et al., 2022). Environmental restrictions encourage sustainable business practices, but their minimal impact suggests they won't change green logistics. The standardised organisational culture (OC) estimate is 0.080, with a p-value less than 0.005, showing a small but statistically significant effect on GLM (Füchtenhans et al., 2023). According to these findings, green logistics is not only driven by a company culture that rewards environmental responsibility.

These findings suggest that logistical fragmentation or a lack of fully integrated sustainability objectives among supply chain partners may limit the supply chain collaboration's impact on green logistics (Amjad et al., 2022). SCI might boost green logistics with greater integration and stronger alliances focused on environmental aims. EEO had a small but significant effect on GLM (standardized estimate = 0.083, $p < 0.004$ in Table 2 (Taghavi, 2022; Jinru et al., 2021).

Conclusions and policy recommendations

Conclusions

Based on the survey, 800 managers related to the logistics activities of enterprises, including Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai Province, Binh Duong Province, and Ba Ria-Vung Tau Province. The data survey is from 15/01/2024 to 15/06/2024 to evaluate the modified scale. The sample size was 800 logistics managers, with only 745 votes processed. The analysis showed eight critical factors affecting green logistics management and revealed a multi-faceted framework where certain elements exert a more substantial influence on green logistics management. Moreover, the authors' key conclusions include technological advancements and innovations as the primary driver with a significant positive impact and underscore the importance of technology in achieving sustainable logistics. While these factors play important roles, especially in setting standards and fostering partnerships, they require complementary efforts from enterprises to achieve substantial improvements in sustainability. This set of recommendations aligns policy interventions with the level of influence each factor has on green logistics management, as indicated by the standardized estimates to enhance green logistics management.

(1) Improve technological advancements and innovations based on the standardized estimate of 0.532. Given the substantial impact on green logistics management, enterprises should incentivise technological investments. Policymakers should prioritize fiscal incentives, such as tax credits, subsidies, or grants, for logistics companies investing in green technologies. This includes funding for electric vehicles, automated warehousing, and renewable energy installations to drive innovation in logistics.

(2) Improve the resource availability and sustainable sourcing based on the standardized estimate of 0.174. Therefore, the government should mandate that logistics companies buy goods and resources from certified sustainable vendors. These guidelines can favor recyclable materials, eco-friendly fuels, and renewable energy in logistics. Corporations should provide subsidies or preferential tax rates to local material suppliers to reduce transportation-related carbon emissions.

(3) Improve the waste minimization and sustainable packaging based on the standardized estimate of 0.123. Therefore, the government should require logistics companies to use recyclable or biodegradable packaging. Policymakers could set clear logistics waste reduction targets and

timelines with packaging rules. Give logistics firms grants or low-interest loans to invest in circular economy techniques, including recycling, reverse logistics, and waste reduction.

(4) Improve the corporate social responsibility based on the standardized estimate of 0.087. Therefore, businesses should require logistics companies to declare environmental impact in CSR filings. This covers emissions, waste reduction, and sustainable resource utilization data, making business sustainability transparent and accountable. Businesses could implement a government-endorsed award or certification scheme for logistics businesses with excellent green CSR practices.

(5) Improve the environmental regulations and policies based on the standardized estimate 0.084. Therefore, the government should tighten emissions, waste management, and logistical sustainability rules to improve environmental compliance. Mandatory environmental audits and fines for non-compliance can enforce compliance. Green logistics certification: Introduce a government-backed accreditation for logistics firms that routinely meet ecological criteria.

(6) Improve the energy efficiency in operations based on the standardized estimate of 0.083. Therefore, warehouses, distribution centers, and transportation fleets in logistics operations should have energy efficiency criteria set by the government. These standards should benchmark energy use and stimulate energy-saving solutions in companies.

(7) Improve the organizational culture based on the standardized estimate of 0.080. Therefore, the government should introduce certification programs that accredit enterprises with environmentally compatible organizational cultures to promote green culture through certification and training. Encourage logistics organizations to train personnel on sustainable practices and environmental awareness to instill sustainability in their principles.

(8) Improve the supply chain collaboration and integration based on the standardized estimate of 0.079. Therefore, the government should support shared logistics platforms or hubs where enterprises may collaborate on distribution, warehousing, and transportation to lessen environmental effects. These platforms could help reduce emissions and waste by sharing resources and consolidating logistics. Encourage logistics providers, manufacturers, and suppliers to form green collaborations.

Limitations and future research: Vietnam's logistics and transportation sectors may dominate the study's sample. Economic, regulatory, and technological issues differ; hence, the conclusions may not apply to other countries or situations due to the specific focus. The study may have ignored perspectives from government agencies or environmental advocacy groups. The research addresses eight essential characteristics that affect green logistics management, although it may have neglected others. This analysis ignores legal restraints from international trade agreements, economic incentives, and customer demand for eco-friendly products, which could affect green logistics adoption. Future research could benefit from a longitudinal approach to green logistics. In response to changing environmental policies and consumer tastes, technical advances, new legislation, and company culture change throughout time. Future research should examine international trade limits, digital change, and customer desire for sustainable products to influence green logistics management.

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